

Digital Marketing Strategy in Increasing Sales of MSMEs: A Case Study of Convection in Samong Village

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore the effectiveness of digital marketing strategies in increasing sales of convection Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Samong Village. The transformation of digital technology has significantly changed the marketing landscape, including among MSME players who have limited resources. Convection businesses in this village have begun to utilize social media and e-commerce platforms such as Shopee, TikTok, Facebook, and Instagram to expand market reach and increase sales. This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. Data were collected through observation, interviews, and direct documentation of convection MSMEs. The results show that digital marketing strategies have a positive impact on increasing brand awareness, expanding the market, and creating a more interactive relationship with consumers. Visual content, such as product photos and live streaming videos, is the main means of attracting customer attention. This strategy supports the Integrated Marketing Communication theory (Kotler & Keller) and the Resource-Based View approach (Barney), which emphasizes the importance of internal resource management and integrated communication. Nonetheless, challenges such as low digital literacy, limited funds for promotion, and price competition from products outside the region are still obstacles. Therefore, training, technical assistance, and support from the government and strategic partners are needed to help convection MSMEs maximize the potential of digital marketing. Thus, this strategy can act as a promotional tool as well as a means of adaptation and growth in a competitive digital era.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital marketing is one of the most popular marketing strategies in today's digital era. Digital marketing uses digital technologies such as the internet, social media, and mobile devices to promote products or services and reach a wider range of consumers. The definition of digital marketing is a marketing activity or promotion of a brand or product using digital media or the internet. The purpose of digital marketing is to attract consumers and potential consumers quickly. Advances in communication and information technology gave birth to social media, from which one can communicate and connect with various parties around the world [1]. With digital marketing, it can improve marketing

strategies and become the right choice in the current era [2].

Although digital marketing is very relevant in the current era, there is one important element that must be considered by MSME economic actors in the digital era, namely networking. Networking allows MSMEs to connect with relevant business partners, customers, and communities so that they can expand their business reach [3]. The problem faced by convection MSMEs in Samong Village when building a network is that it is difficult to build their own network. Small and medium-sized businesses (MSMEs) such as convection often have limited resources, both in terms of capital and in terms of human resources. As the times develop, many competitors are already using digital marketing techniques, this causes the lag of

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convection businesses in Samong village due to a lack of understanding in digital matters.

According to Coviello, Milley, and Marcollin in 2001, they argue that digital marketing is the use of web media and other intuitive innovations to connect buyers and organizations and can easily share data and convey [4]. According to Chaffey, digital marketing is the use of digital technology to create online channels to market (through websites, email, databases, digital television, and other means [5]. The conclusion from the two opinions above is that digital marketing is the use of technology and digital media to connect buyers with organizations and create online channels to market, such as through websites, email, and other digital media. To keep up with the times so as not to be left behind by competitors, convection entrepreneurs in Samong Village in addition to conventional marketing now also use digital marketing techniques. The products produced are marketed through social media such as shopee and tiktok.

Small and medium enterprise (SME) marketing has changed from conventional to digital marketing using social media and websites. SMEs can grow their business by using online media. Before SMEs finally decide to use online media as a way to expand their business reach, their main reasons are the ease of access to the internet today, the many benefits it offers, and the affordable cost. SMEs that are internet-based, engaged in social media, and thriving in e-commerce will usually enjoy significant business advantages in terms of revenue, employment opportunities, innovation, and competitiveness [6].

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play an important role in driving economic growth, dynamics, and development. In Indonesia, MSMEs dominate the business sector due to their large number, covering small to medium-sized enterprises. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen and empower MSMEs so that they can develop more optimally and contribute to maintaining national economic stability. Empowering MSMEs is a key strategy to increase productivity and advance the sector. In addition to focusing on increasing production, it is also necessary to expand the market, considering that many MSMEs in Indonesia have difficulty developing due to limitations in marketing reach. One strategy that can be applied is digital marketing, which allows products to reach consumers faster and on target. However, currently there are still few MSMEs in Indonesia that utilize digital marketing as a marketing tool. In fact, in the current digital era, buying and selling transactions are increasingly being carried out through digital platforms because they are

considered more practical, both for consumers and sellers [7]. The high competition in the convection industry and changes in people's consumption patterns that are increasingly shifting to online shopping are the main reasons for the need for a digital marketing strategy for convection MSMEs in Samong Village. By understanding and implementing effective digital marketing techniques, it is hoped that convection MSMEs in Samong Village can survive and thrive in the digital era.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the challenges faced by convection MSMEs in product marketing and explore digital marketing strategies that can increase convection sales in Samong Village. In a digital marketing strategy, one of the goals is to gain an advantage in many competitors. In today's crucial digital and internet era is a new advancement in marketing strategies. Thanks to online marketing strategies, sectors such as micro, small, and medium enterprises have the potential to generate significant profits. As a result, every SME should make the most of digital marketing.

The results show that, as a result of many similar businesses, convection entrepreneurs have become more competitive in terms of marketing. Businesses that do not implement and create appropriate marketing strategies risk losing customers. In addition, businesses cannot compete in marketing their products because they must anticipate the competition, i.e. choose the right marketing strategy and run the business efficiently. Making products superior and attracting customer attention is a marketing strategy that can be done. Since there are many similar competing products, convection MSME entrepreneurs must use digital marketing strategies to stay above their competitors in the market. Convection in Samong Village only uses conventional marketing. However, they have implemented online marketing using various platforms such as shopee and tiktok.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The method used for the continuity of this research, the author uses a qualitative method with a case study approach. The data source of data in this study uses primary data, namely making observations, interviews and documentation. Data collection techniques using observation, interviews and documentation. This research took place in Samong Village, Ulujami District, Pemalang Regency.

3. RESULTS

Based on the results of interviews and observations of convection MSMEs in Samong

Village, it is known that most business actors have begun to utilize digital marketing strategies as an effort to increase sales and expand the market. The most widely used platforms are Shopee, TikTok, Facebook, and Instagram. Through these platforms, MSME players create attractive visual content and conduct live streaming regularly to promote products.

The use of social media and marketplaces has proven to help businesses introduce their products more widely, not only in the surrounding area, but also to various regions in Indonesia. Features such as customer reviews, digital payment systems (e-wallets), and discount and flash sale programs are also used to attract consumers.

However, several obstacles were found in the implementation, such as low digital literacy, lack of technical skills in managing digital content, and limited promotional funds to use paid advertising features. In addition, competition with cheaper products from outside the region is also a significant challenge for convection MSME players in Samong Village.

4. DISCUSSION

The effectiveness of digital marketing strategies in increasing sales of convection MSMEs in Samong Village Based on the results of an interview with one of the convection MSME players in Samong Village, that Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Samong Village began to utilize digital marketing strategies as an effort to increase sales and expand their market reach. This strategy has proven to be quite effective, especially for businesses in the convection sector that previously only relied on offline sales or through conventional channels. Based on the research results, convection business owners in Samong Village have utilized various digital platforms and popular marketplaces such as Shopee, TikTok, Facebook, and Instagram. Through these platforms, they can introduce their products more widely to the community, not only in the surrounding area but also to various regions in Indonesia. This utilization of social media and e-commerce provides a great opportunity to increase brand awareness, build more interactive communication with customers, and adjust marketing strategies based on consumer trends and preferences. Thus, digital marketing is one of the important factors in helping convection MSMEs in Samong Village survive and compete in the midst of increasingly competitive market challenges.

In the digital era that continues to grow rapidly, Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

(MSMEs) in Samong Village have begun to utilize digital marketing strategies as an effort to increase sales and expand their market reach. This strategy is in line with the theory of *Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) theory according to Kotler and Keller (2016)*, which states that marketing is a process that involves planning, implementing, and monitoring activities to create, communicate, and deliver value to customers and manage relationships in a way that is profitable for the Company [8]. MSME business actors in Samong Village utilize social media platforms as a sales implementation that can increase communication with customers in various regions through social media.

This research is also supported by Enderwati et al. that this research focuses on empowering convection business actors in Jurangmangu through social media training. The results show that good social media account management has an impact on increasing visits and sales [9]. This is the same as the research being carried out, that convection business actors in Samong Village who used to only sell conventionally until now online can increase sales. So that social media strategies can empower convection business actors to be more independent and highly competitive.

Utilization of social media and marketplaces as a digital marketing strategy for convection MSMEs in Samong Village

Social media and marketplaces are the main tools as digital marketing strategies for convection MSMEs in Samong village. MSME players utilize Shopee, Tiktok, Facebook, Instagram to promote their products. In promoting their products, MSME players create interesting product content and also carry out live streaming consistently. By using social media and marketplaces, buyers can easily make purchases that do not need to go directly to the field and can pay using E-wallets. In addition, MSME players can easily participate in flash sale or discount programs to attract more customers. With the marketplace and also social media, there are also rating and review features from customers that can give confidence to potential buyers.

Social media and marketplaces have become key components in the digital marketing strategy implemented by convection MSMEs in Samong Village. Businesses utilize various platforms such as Shopee, TikTok, Facebook, and Instagram to market their products widely. This utilization is in accordance with the *digital marketing mix* theory according to Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick [8], which explains that digital marketing or online marketing is a series of marketing strategies and techniques

that use the internet and online platforms to promote products, services, or brands. The goal is to attract the attention of the target audience, increase traffic to the website or product page, and ultimately convert prospects into customers. In practice, many MSMEs in Samong Village currently use social media platforms such as shopee, tiktok, Instagram, and facebook to promote and sell their products by creating interesting content and live streaming. In addition, social media is also used to interact with their customers through chat, commenting on live, or giving reviews on their products.

According to Effendi & Anshory [10], that marketing based on interesting content and live streaming can increase consumer attention and trust. This is the same as the convection MSME players in Samong Village who use e-commerce by creating interesting video content and live streaming. Visual content strategies and live streaming increase awareness and facilitate the buying process directly from social media.

Barriers to the implementation of digital marketing for convection MSMEs in Samong Village

Although the digital marketing strategy has helped increase sales of convection MSMEs, there are still some obstacles in its implementation. Some MSME players still have difficulties in optimally operating digital platforms. In addition, not all MSME players have an adequate budget to carry out paid promotions consistently, such as advertisements on social media or paid features in the marketplace. This is an obstacle in reaching a wider audience and building brand awareness quickly. Many outside convection products sell at lower prices, so Samong Village MSME players must put more effort into competing. On the other hand, intense market competition is also a challenge. Many convection products from outside the region are sold at much cheaper prices, thus requiring MSME players in Samong Village to continue to improve product quality and creativity in promotion in order to be able to compete.

Barney's theory [11] states that the competitive advantage of an organization is determined by its resources, both tangible and intangible. These resources must be valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable, and nonsubstitutable in order to provide a sustainable competitive advantage. In the study, some convection MSME players in Samong Village were still unskilled in implementing online sales. In addition, they must also further increase creativity so that the products sold can compete with other products.

According to Kusnandar et al. [12], that the lack of digital literacy and technological skills is the main inhibiting factor for the digital

transformation of MSMEs. Some MSME players in Samong Village also still do not understand the effective use of e-commerce. Many MSME players are not familiar with advertising features, creative content management, or e-commerce utilization, which has an impact on the low effectiveness of digital marketing strategies.

5. Conclusion

This research shows that the digital marketing strategy implemented by convection MSMEs in Samong Village has had a positive impact in increasing sales and expanding market reach. The use of social media and marketplace platforms such as Shopee, TikTok, Instagram, and Facebook are actively utilized by businesses in promoting products through attractive visual content, live streaming, and direct interaction with customers. However, in addition to its effectiveness, this study also revealed significant obstacles, such as limited understanding of digital technology, lack of budget for paid promotion, and price competition with convection products from outside the region.

Theoretically, these findings support the Integrated Marketing Communication theory (Kotler & Keller, 2016) as well as the Resource-Based View theory by Barney (1991), which emphasizes the importance of resource management, including digital resources and technological skills as strategic capital. The practical implication is that this research emphasizes the importance of training and technical assistance for MSME players to be better able to optimize the use of digital media in their marketing activities. The support of government agencies or strategic partners in providing access to training, advertising capital, and digital collaboration is an important key in empowering MSMEs in rural areas

For future research, it is recommended that a quantitative approach be taken with a wider range of respondents to see the correlation between the use of digital marketing strategies and numerical income increases. Researchers can also explore effective empowerment models for local community-based MSMEs, as well as examine more deeply the role of local governments and digital stakeholders in supporting the digital transformation of MSMEs in other villages. Further research can also review aspects of online consumer behavior in choosing convection MSME products so that promotional strategies can be tailored more specifically and personally.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper. All authors have contributed equally to this research and publication. Furthermore, this study did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Ethics Committee

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of academic research. Since the research involved interviews and observations with local MSME actors without collecting sensitive personal data, formal ethics approval was not required under institutional guidelines of UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan. Prior informed consent was obtained from all participants involved in the study.

Author Contributions

Lisa Dwi Amelia: Conceptualization, data collection, methodology, formal analysis, writing original draft preparation; Hendri Hermawan Adinugraha: Supervision, theoretical framework validation, writing review and editing; Ade Gunawan: Literature review, visualization, data interpretation, proofreading. All authors have read and approved the final version of the manuscript for publication.

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